

SYNTHESIS OF COUMARINS FROM *o*-HYDROXY-ARYL-ALKYL KETONES. PART III.

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In continuation of the new method of synthesis of coumarins from *o*-hydroxy-aryl-alkyl ketone it has been found that when there is an alkyl substituent in the β -position of the expected cinnamic ester coumarin is invariably formed irrespective of the presence of any substituent in the α -position, the presence of any alkyl group or a halogen atom in the benzene nucleus of the ketone having without any appreciable effect on the reaction. Thus 4-alkylcoumarins and 3:4-dialkylcoumarins have been prepared in excellent yield.

The *o*-hydroxyaryl-alkyl ketones have been conveniently used by Chakravarti and Majumdar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **15**, 136) for the synthesis of coumarin derivatives. They have also observed that *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde, 5-chloro-*o*-methoxybenzaldehyde and β -resorcylaldehyde dimethyl ether, when condensed with ethyl bromoacetate or ethyl α -bromopropionate form *o*-coumaric acid derivatives which do not lactonise readily (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 389).

The present investigation has been undertaken with a view (i) to study the effect of various substituents, *e.g.* alkyl, Cl, Br, etc., in different positions in the phenyl nucleus of the *o*-hydroxy-aryl-alkyl ketones on the formation of coumarins.

(ii) and secondly to study the influence of substituents in the α - and β -positions of the cinnamic ester to be formed on the formation of *o*-coumaric acids in the above synthesis.

The methoxy derivatives of the following ketones, *viz.*, 5-chloro-2-hydroxy-, 5-bromo-2-hydroxy-, 3-methyl-2-hydroxy-, 5-methyl-2-hydroxy-, 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxy-, 5-chloro-4-methyl-2-hydroxy-, 5-methyl-3-chloro-2-hydroxy-acetophenones, 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxy-, 3-chloro-5-methyl-2-hydroxy-propiofenones have been condensed with ethyl bromoacetate and ethyl- α -bromopropionate according to Reformatsky forming hydroxy-esters, which are treated with thionyl chloride and pyridine to yield unsaturated esters. The latter on treatment with hydriodic acid or on keeping with concentrated sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84) overnight give quantitative yields of the coumarins. It is not absolutely necessary to convert the hydroxy-esters into the unsaturated esters and the former may as well be conveniently utilised for the lactonisation to form coumarins.

The acetophenones and the propiofenones have all been prepared from the corresponding acetyl and the propionyl derivatives of the phenols by

heating with aluminium chloride (Fries rearrangement). It has been observed that in some cases an appreciable amount of phenol results, obviously from the deacetylation or depropionylation of the acetyl or propionyl derivatives as the case might be. The formation of the phenol is effectively overcome by heating with aluminium chloride for half an hour at 130-40°.

Some of the coumarins, synthesised by this method, have been found to be identical (m.p. and mixed m.p.) with the compounds described by Chakravarti and Banerjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 619) by the application of Pechmann's reaction on the phenols or by Chakravarti and Majumdar (*ibid.*, 1939, 16, 151) by Kostanecki's reaction on *o*-hydroxy-acetophenones.

It is evident, therefore, that when there is an alkyl substituent in the β -position of the expected cinnamic ester, coumarin is invariably formed, irrespective of the presence of any substituent in the α -position. Thus 4-alkylcoumarins and 3:4-dialkylcoumarins may readily be synthesised from the appropriate *o*-hydroxy-aryl-alkyl ketones, the presence of any alkyl group or a halogen atom in the benzene nucleus of the ketone having without any appreciable effect on the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL.

5-Chloro-2-methoxyacetophenone.—A solution of 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone (20 g.) in alcoholic sodium ethoxide (2.7 g. of sodium in 60 c.c. of alcohol) was heated on the water-bath with methyl iodide (20 g.) for about 3 hours. The excess of alcohol was distilled off and the methoxy derivative was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with a dilute solution of caustic soda and then with water, dried and distilled. It was obtained as a colourless thick oil, b.p. 135°/6 mm. It solidifies on chilling in ice. (Found: Cl, 19.24. $C_8H_9O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 19.24 per cent).

Ethyl 2-Methoxy-5-chloro- β -methylcinnamate.—A mixture of 2-methoxy-5-chloroacetophenone (7 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (11 g.), zinc wool (5 g.) and benzene (25 c.c.) was heated on a water-bath for 2-2½ hours, when the zinc dissolved. The solution was then poured into ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid, the benzene layer was separated, washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and with water and then dried. On removing benzene it was distilled at 155.60°/5 mm. as a thick light yellow oil, yield 6.5 g. The hydroxy-ester (6.5 g.) was converted into the unsaturated ester with thionyl chloride (2.5 c.c.) in presence of pyridine (3 c.c.) in dry ethereal solution (100 c.c.). After decomposing excess of thionyl chloride with ice the ethereal layer was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, sodium carbonate and finally with water. On removing ether the product was distilled at 155°/5 mm.

TABLE I.

Name of the compound.	Mol. formula.	Prepared from	Analysis Found.	Theo.	M.p. or B.p.	Remarks.
5-Bromo-2-methoxy-acetophenone. (I)	$C_9H_9O_2Br$	5-Bromo-2-hydroxy-acetophenone	Br, 34.94	34.93	$165^{\circ}/12$ mm.	Colourless thick oil
Ethyl 2-methoxy-5-bromo- β -methylcinna-mate (Ia)	$C_{11}H_{15}O_3Br$	(I) and ethyl bromoacetate and then dehydrated	26.71	26.75	$180^{\circ}/8$ mm.	Colourless oil
4-Methyl-6-bromocoumarin.	$C_{10}H_7O_2Br$	(Ia) using H_2SO_4	33.37	33.47	187°	Needles from spirit
Ethyl 2-methoxy-5-bromo- β -dimethylcinna-mate. (Ib)	$C_{14}H_{17}O_3Br$	(I) and ethyl α -bromopropionate and then dehydrated.	Br, 25.36	25.55	$169-70^{\circ}/10$ mm.	Colourless oil
3,4-Dimethyl-6-bromocoumarin	$C_{11}H_9O_2Br$	(Ib) using H_2SO_4	31.71	31.58	169°	Needles from dilute alcohol
5-Methyl-2-methoxyacetophenone (II)	$C_{10}H_{13}O_2$	3-Methyl-2-hydroxy-acetophenone	C, 73.2 H, 7.5	73.17 7.3	$120^{\circ}/13$ mm.	Colourless oil
Ethyl 2-methoxy-3-methyl- β -methylcinna-mate (IIa)	$C_{14}H_{18}O_3$	(II) and ethyl bromoacetate and then dehydrated	C, 71.61 H, 7.7	71.79 7.69	$140-42^{\circ}/9$ mm.	Colourless oil
*4, β -Dimethylcoumarin	$C_{11}H_{10}O_2$	(IIa) using H_2SO_4	C, 76.13 H, 5.9	75.86 5.74	114°	Crystallised from dilute alcohol as needles
*5-Methyl-2-methoxyacetophenone (III)	$C_{10}H_{13}O_2$	5-Methyl-2-hydroxy-acetophenone	C, 73.11 H, 7.2	73.17 7.3	$110^{\circ}/6$ mm.	Colourless oil

as a colourless oil, yield 3 g. (Found : Cl, 14.06. $C_{12}H_{16}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 13.94 per cent).

4-Methyl-6-chlorocoumarin.—The above unsaturated ester (1 g.) was kept overnight with sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 6 c.c.). The solution was treated with powdered ice and the solid obtained was crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 184° , yield quantitative. The ring-closure was also effected by heating the unsaturated ester with hydriodic acid (d 1.7, 6 c.c.) at 140° for 2 hours. (Found : Cl, 18.58. $C_{10}H_7O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 18.25 per cent). The coumarins described in this paper were all prepared in the above way and they are described in Table I

TABLE I (contd.).

Name of the compound.	Mol. formula.	Prepared from	Found, Analysis	M.p. or B.p.	Remarks.
			Theo.		
Ethyl 2-methoxy-3-methyl- β -methylcinamate (IIIa)	$C_{14}H_{18}O_3$	(III) and ethyl bromoacetate and then dehydrated	C, 71.54 H, 7.79	166°/12 mm	Colourless oil
4- δ -Dimethylcoumarin	...	(IIIa) using H_2SO_4		150°	Identical with the compound described by Chakravarti and Banerjee (<i>loc. cit.</i>)
Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dimethyl- β -hydroxy- β (2-methoxy-5-methyl)-phenyl propionate (IIIb)	$C_{13}H_{18}O_4$	(III) and ethyl α -bromopropionate	C, 67.83 H, 8.06	67-67 8-47	Colourless oil
3:4:5-Trimethylcoumarin	...	(IIIb) using H_2SO_4	...	170°	Identical with the compound described by Chakravarti (<i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1932, 9, 29) (mixed m.p.)
5-Chloro-3-methyl-2-methoxypropiofenone (IV)	$C_{11}H_{13}O_2Cl$	5-Chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxypropiofenone (Chakravarti and Majumdar, <i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1939, 16, 155)	Cl, 16.6	16.7	Oil with a yellow tinge
Ethyl 2-methoxy-3-methyl-5-chloro- α -methyl- β -ethylcinamate (IVa)	$C_{16}H_{21}O_2Cl$	(IV) and ethyl α -bromopropionate and then dehydrated	Cl, 12.3	11.96	Colourless oil
3- β -Dimethyl-4-ethyl-6-chlorocoumarin	$C_{13}H_{17}O_2Cl$	(IVa) using H_2SO_4 or HI	Cl, 15.17	15.1	Fine needles from dilute alcohol
3-Chloro-5-methyl-2-methoxypropiofenone (V)	$C_{11}H_{13}O_2Cl$	3-Chloro-5-methyl-2-hydroxypropiofenone	Cl, 16.5	16.7	Colourless oil

TABLE I (contd.).

Name of the compound.	Mol. formula.	Prepared from	Analysis Found.	Analysis Theo.	M.p. or B.p.	Remarks.
Ethyl 2-methoxy-3-chloro-5-methyl- α -methyl- β -ethylcoumarate (Va)	$C_{18}H_{21}O_4Cl$	(V) and ethyl α -bromopropionate and then dehydrated	Cl, 12.0	11.96	160°/8 mm.	Colourless oil
3:5-Dimethyl-4-ethyl-8-chlorocoumarin	$C_{19}H_{23}O_2Cl$	(Va) using H_2SO_4 or HI	Cl, 15.2	15.01	120°	Needles from dilute alcohol
5-Chloro-3-methyl-2-methoxyacetophenone (VI)	$C_{10}H_{13}O_2Cl$	5-Chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone (Chakravarti and Majumdar, <i>loc. cit.</i>)	Cl, 17.7	17.8	136°/8 mm.	Light yellow oil
Ethyl 2-methoxy-3-methyl-5-chloro- β -methylcoumarate (VIa)	$C_{14}H_{17}O_4Cl$	(VI) and ethyl bromoacetate and then dehydrated	Cl, 13.4	13.2	163°/5 mm.	Colourless oil
4:5-Dimethyl-6-chlorocoumarin	$C_{11}H_{13}O_2Cl$	(VIa) using H_2SO_4	Cl, 17.5	17.02	155°	Needles from dilute alcohol
Ethyl 2-methoxy-3-methyl-5-chloro- α - β -dimethylcoumarate (VIb)	$C_{16}H_{19}O_4Cl$	(VI) and ethyl α -bromopropionate and then dehydrated	Cl, 12.8	12.96	165°/7 mm.	Colourless oil
3:4:8-Trimethyl-6-chlorocoumarin	...	(VIb) using H_2SO_4 or HI	..	...	†124°	Identical with the compound described by Chakravarti and Majumdar (<i>loc. cit.</i>) (mixed m.p.)

† The m.p. of the compound as recorded by Chakravarti and Majumdar (m.p. 94°) was found to be incorrect as the m.p. rose to 124° on recrystallisation.

TABLE I (contd.).

Name of the compound.	Mol. formula.	Prepared from	Found.	Analysis Theo.	M.p. or B.p.	Remarks.
5-Chloro-3-methyl-4-methoxyacetophenone (VII)	$C_{10}H_{11}O_2Cl$	5-Chloro-3-methyl-4-hydroxyacetophenone	Cl, 17.7	17.8	61°	Colourless needles from dilute alcohol
Ethyl 2-methoxy-4-methyl-5-chloro-6-methylcinnamate (VIIa)	$C_{14}H_{17}O_4Cl$	(VII) and ethyl bromoacetate and then dehydrated	Cl, 13.8	13.3	160°/5 mm.	Colourless oil
4-7-Dimethyl-6-chloro coumarin	...	(VIIa) using H_2SO_4 or HI	...	...	213°	Identical with the compound described by Chakravarti and Banerjee (<i>loc. cit.</i>) (mixed m.p.)
Ethyl 2-methoxy-4-methyl-5-chloro-6-dimethylcinnamate (VII b)	$C_{15}H_{19}O_4Cl$	(VII) and ethyl α -bromopropionate and then dehydrated	Cl, 12.7	12.56	160°/3 mm.	Colourless oil
3:4:7-Trimethyl-6-chloro coumarin	...	(VIIb) using H_2SO_4 or HI	...	...	167°	Identical with the compound described by Chakravarti and Banerjee (<i>loc. cit.</i>) (mixed m.p.)
5-Methyl-3-chloro-2-methoxyacetophenone (VIII)	$C_{10}H_{11}O_3Cl$	5-Methyl-3-chloro-4-hydroxyacetophenone	Cl, 17.6	17.8	124°/4 mm.	Colourless oil

† The m.p. of Chakravarti and Banerjee's compound (recorded as 146°) rose to 167° on further crystallisation.

TABLE I (contd.).

Name of the compound.	Mol. formula.	Prepared from	Analysis Found.	M.p. or B.p.	Remarks.
Ethyl 2-methoxy-3-chloro-5-methyl-6-methylcinnamate (VIIIa)	$C_{17}H_{17}O_2Cl$	(VIII) and ethyl bromoacetate and then dehydrated	Cl, 13.41	160°/6 mm.	Colourless oil
4:6-Dimethyl-8-chlorocoumarin.	...	(VIIIa) and H_2SO_4	...	148°	Identical with the compound described by Chakravarti and Banerjee (<i>loc. cit.</i>) (mixed m.p.)
Ethyl 2-methoxy-3-chloro-5-methyl-4-β-dimethylcinnamate (VIIIb)	$C_{18}H_{19}O_2Cl$	(VIII) and ethyl α-bromopropionate and then dehydrated	Cl, 12.59	170°/9 mm.	Colourless oil
3:4:6-Trimethyl-8-chlorocoumarin	...	(VIIIb) and HI	...	133°	Needles from dilute alcohol. Identical with the compound described by Chakravarti and Majumdar (<i>loc. cit.</i>) (mixed m.p.)

* The analyses of compounds marked with * are micro-analyses done by Mr. N. Ghosh of the University College of Science, to whom our best thanks are due.

